

ISic0167

I.Sicily inscription 0167

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 84

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Daphne

2. vix(it) ann(is) XXIII

3. Canini Agonis

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Daphne, (wife?) of Caninus Agon, lived 23 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285261

EDR 127476

EDCS 22100100

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7398a (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650799>)

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Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 88
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 98

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